

**Empowering leadership and innovative work behavior: The
mediating effects of climate for initiative and job autonomy in Moroccan
SMEs**

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Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of this paper was to explore the role of empowering leadership, organizational climate for initiative and job autonomy in spurring innovative work behavior (IWB).

Design/methodology/approach: We resorted to the Structural Equation Modelling technique along the Bayesian estimation approach to analyze the mediating role of the organizational climate for initiative and job autonomy in the empowering leadership-IWB link in data gathered from CEOs, middle managers and non-managerial employees of 444 small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Morocco.

Findings: The findings revealed that empowering leadership is a prerequisite of IWB as subordinates, who are empowered by their leaders, demonstrate IWB. Further, organizational climate for initiative and job autonomy mediate the empowering leadership-IWB link.

Practical implications: This research has demonstrated that firms and organizational leaders who seek to make their middle managers innovative in their job should adopt empowering leadership practices, build an organizational climate that is favorable for initiative-taking and grant middle managers with autonomy in the way they carry out their tasks.

Originality: This paper extends our understanding on the mechanisms linking empowering leadership and IWB by testing the mediating effects of organizational climate for initiative and job autonomy.

Keywords: Empowering leadership; climate for initiative; job autonomy; innovative work behavior.

Introduction

Innovative work behavior (IWB) refers to the generation and implementation of new ideas at work (Escribá-Carda *et al.*, 2017). While the idea generation phase is the entry gate to the entire innovation process (Abdel Aziz and Rizkallah, 2015) through identifying innovative solutions with the objective of seizing an opportunity or addressing a given problem, idea implementation is concerned with the phase of implementing innovative ideas at work (Scott and Bruce, 1994).

IWB has been extensively found to be important for the organization's survival (Pieterse *et al.*, 2010), benefits (Yuan and Woodman, 2010) and competitiveness (Shanker *et al.*, 2017); this importance is reflected in the development of new products, services and organizational procedures, employee and firm effectiveness, and employee job satisfaction (Janssen *et al.*, 2004). The prominent role that IWB plays at work has exhorted scholars to examine its positive associations with various factors such as work climate, leadership and personal traits (see Anderson *et al.*, 2004; Hammond *et al.*, 2011).

It has been suggested that IWB is considerably contingent on organizational interactions (Anderson *et al.*, 2004). As such, organizations can not be innovative without their members (Birkinshaw *et al.*, 2008), including leaders (Hassi, 2019; Vaccaro *et al.*, 2012). In fact, leaders exert tremendous influence on subordinates' IWB (Basadur, 2004). Given this context, the importance of leaders' role in organizational innovation has begun to attract the attention of scholars (see Caridi-Zahavi *et al.*, 2015; Chen *et al.*, 2014). Specifically, empowering leadership is a promising leadership style to examine in this regard given its enabling facets as reflected in its

positive effect on IWB (Cheong *et al.*, 2016) and the fact that it intends to create autonomous and self-directed individuals.

Empowering leadership can be defined as a style of leadership that is mostly characterized by “behaviors that share power with subordinates” (Vecchio *et al.*, 2010, p.531). It revolves around the meaning of employees' work, participation in decision making, removal of bureaucratic constraints, and increasing confidence in achieving desired performance (Ahearne *et al.*, 2005). Empowering leadership also exhorts subordinates to display pro-active behaviors (Martin *et al.*, 2013) owing to the trust and confidence exhibited by empowering leaders (Tuckey *et al.*, 2012). Thus, it is understandable why empowering leadership exerts a positive effect on creativity (Zhang and Zhou, 2014), management innovation (Hassi, 2019) as well as product innovation, process innovation, and administrative innovation (Lim and Gon, 2021). However, only limited research has examined links between empowering leadership and IWB (Jada *et al.*, 2019) and in a few industries, namely education (see Gkorezis 2016), hospitality (Slåtten *et al.*, 2011; Wihuda *et al.*, 2017), and the pharmaceutical industry (see Jada *et al.*, 2019), and only in Western and Asian countries.

Further, these studies have mostly explored how job-linked factors, such as role conflict, knowledge sharing and role clarity, interplay between empowering leadership and IWB, while the role of other contextual antecedents of innovation such as climate for initiative and job autonomy have yet to be examined. Therefore, research is considerably needed to bridge this gap. In fact, researchers have scarcely investigated the impact of the interaction between leadership and organizational climate on innovation (Si and Wei, 2012). In this respect, climate for initiative, which translates the degree to which a work environment is more or less supportive of personal

initiative, is a determinant of behavior at work (Baer and Frese, 2003); this is due to the fact that it significantly influences individuals' proactivity by means of impacting their mindset in regard to whether they can behave certain ways and on their motivation to behave that particular way (Parker *et al.*, 2010).

On another note, as the nature of work is constantly and drastically changing and affecting work processes and organizational structures in present-day organizations (Wegman *et al.*, 2018), workers are pursuing increased flexibility and autonomy at work (Grant *et al.*, 2011). Job autonomy is defined as “*the degree to which the job provides substantial freedom, independence, and discretion to the individual in scheduling the work and in determining the procedures to be used in carrying it out*” (Hackman and Oldham, 1976, p. 258). Therefore, organizations generally identify ways to promote innovation by emphasizing job autonomy (Mankins and Garton, 2017); particularly, job characteristics (i.e., autonomy) have been shown to act as a driving force for IWB (Oldham and Cummings, 1996; Shipton *et al.*, 2016).

In following the appeal to conducting research on business practices that promote the implementation of innovative behavior (Michaelis *et al.*, 2010), the present study aims at shedding light on the relationship between empowering leadership and IWB along the mediating effects of climate for initiative and job autonomy (see Figure 1) within small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in manufacturing industries. In so doing, the current paper investigates the non-linear main effects of empowering leadership on a work-related outcome, namely IWB as recommended by Cheong *et al.* (2019).

We resort to CEOs' empowering leadership as it is relevant to innovation processes within organizations (Lee *et al.*, 2020; Lee *et al.*, 2018). Similarly, middle managers are key players in organizational innovations (Floyd and Wooldridge, 2017; Heyden *et al.*, 2018) owing to their knowledge of their firms and markets (Chen *et al.*, 2018) as well as to their ability to make important innovation accessible to top managers and to contribute original knowledge in the innovation endeavors (Glaser *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 1. Hypothesized model of mediation

Research hypotheses

Empowering leadership and IWB

IWB is pre-determined by different contextual factors (Naglieri and Kaufman, 2001) such as empowering leadership.

Empirical evidence has revealed that empowering leadership is linked to IWB (Jada *et al.*, 2019) in the educational sector (see Gkorezis 2016), hospitality (Slåtten *et al.*, 2011; Wihuda *et al.*, 2017), and the pharmaceutical industry (see Jada *et al.*, 2019). In fact, Jada *et al.* (2019) found that

empowering leadership is linked to IWB as empowering leaders create a climate for IWB by promoting knowledge sharing among their subordinates whose jobs are marked by role clarity. Gkorezis (2016) concluded that empowering leadership and IWB are associated and there is a moderated mediation through exploration and role conflict. Slåtten *et al.* (2011) found that empowering leadership positively affects IWB and this link is mediated by employees' creativity. Wihuda's *et al.* (2017) study revealed that empowering leadership is associated with employee service innovative behavior and this association is mediated by creative improvisation self-efficacy and employee engagement.

Empowering leaders exhort their followers to experiment innovative ways at work without running the risk of being subject to punishment in the advent of negative outcomes of their experiments (Jung *et al.*, 2003). Along the same lines, subordinates, who are empowered by their organizations, demonstrate creative behaviors at work (Chow, 2018) by aligning their desired outcomes with organizational goals as they find meaning in their professional roles (Jung *et al.*, 2003). They are prone to be motivated to promote and exhibit IWB (Krishnan, 2012; Yidong and Xinxin, 2013).

The first hypothesis is thus as follows:

Hypothesis 1: CEOs' empowering leadership is positively associated with middle managers' IWB.

Empowering leadership and organizational climate for initiative

Empowering leaders can promote and favor organizational climate for initiative because they (1) grant subordinates the freedom to take independent decisions (Forrester, 2000), (2) encourage followers to act independently, take initiative, and promptly solve crises they confront at work (Kim and Beehr, 2017), and (3) promote a solid sense of autonomy among followers (Hon and Chan, 2013). Therefore, empowering leadership behavior allows organizations to provide an

initiative-friendly environment to its members. We draw on the above reasoning to argue that empowering leaders favor initiative-taking and build a climate for initiative within their organizations. Thus, we state:

Hypothesis 2: CEOs' empowering leadership is positively associated with climate for initiative.

Organizational climate for initiative and IWB

Climate for initiative is linked to IWB because personal initiative is associated with idea generation (Binnewies *et al.*, 2007) and innovation implementation in the workplace (Michaelis *et al.*, 2010). Organizations with a strong climate for initiative promote IWB because their workers are granted discretion in the way they execute their tasks and they pursue working on their ideas until they transform them into valuable suggestions (Frese *et al.*, 1999). Further, subordinates who consider their organizations as having a strong climate for initiative believe that their senior managers can overcome obstacles in the process of innovation implementation (Michaelis *et al.*, 2010). Building on the above, this hypothesis can be made:

Hypothesis 3: Organizational climate for initiative is positively associated with middle managers' IWB.

Empowering leadership and job autonomy

Research has found that empowering leaders enhance the job autonomy of their subordinates (Arnold *et al.*, 2000; Kim and Beehr, 2017). Conversely, low empowering leaders restrict granting autonomy to their followers (Chen *et al.*, 2011). Hence, we posit that empowering leaders grant subordinates autonomy in their job because of the following considerations. Empowering leaders support follower involvement in decision making and remove bureaucratic curtailments (Ahearne *et al.*, 2005); they also urge subordinates to display pro-active behaviors and promote a solid sense

of autonomy among subordinates (Hon and Chan, 2013). Hence, the following hypothesis can be proposed:

Hypothesis 4: CEOs' empowering leadership positively affects middle managers' job autonomy.

Job autonomy and IWB

Work design theory is rooted in the assumption that some job or task characteristics (e.g., job autonomy) along certain aspects of the broader work environment engenders some psychological states that result in specific work outcomes such as IWB (Morgeson and Humphrey, 2006).

Job autonomy is vital for organizational success because the latter is oftentimes contingent on employees' behaviors that go above and beyond their standard work by demonstrating an increased level of work-related motivation and efforts (Hernaus and Mikulić, 2014), and innovative behavior rather than only performing tasks that are required as part of the job description (Van der Vegt and Janssen, 2003). Along the same line, proximal work context features such as job autonomy have been found to be better predictors of employee creativity than distal features such as organizational policies (Shalley and Gilson, 2004). Particularly, job autonomy has been shown to permit translating innovation-related behaviors into innovation performance (Burcharth *et al.*, 2017).

There is a body of literature supporting the effect of job autonomy on IWB (e.g., De Spiegelaere *et al.*, 2016; Hammond *et al.*, 2011; Slåtten *et al.*, 2011) due to the following considerations. First, individuals are likely to commit to making creative work when they feel that they can choose the way to carry out their tasks (Amabile *et al.*, 1996). Second, job autonomy permits people to experiment with new work-related approaches and techniques (De Spiegelaere *et al.*, 2016). Finally, as Deci and Ryan's (1985) self-determination theory suggests, the sense of autonomy that

individuals feel at work yields a sustained level of motivation to finding and implementing creative solutions. Hence, the following hypothesis can be made.

Hypothesis 5: Middle managers' job autonomy is positively associated with their IWB.

Indirect effects of CEOs' empowering leadership

The relationship between empowering leadership and IWB has been found to be mediated by exploration (Gkorezis 2016), knowledge sharing (Jada *et al.*, 2019), and employee creativity (Slåtten *et al.*, 2011) as well as creative improvisation self-efficacy and employee engagement. (Wihuda's *et al.* (2017). Further, except Slåtten's *et al.* (2011) work, these studies have mostly explored how personal and job-linked factors such as knowledge sharing interplay between empowering leadership and IWB, while the role of other contextual antecedents of innovation such as climate for initiative and job autonomy has yet to be examined. To contribute to bridging this gap, we posit both direct links between empowering leadership and IWB as well as indirect links through climate for initiative and job autonomy.

On one hand, organizational leaders' positive support impacts subordinates' initiative (Ohly *et al.*, 2006) which, in turn, exerts more discretion on the way subordinates perform their jobs (Baer and Frese, 2003). Empirical arguments have suggested that followers who perceive strong levels of climate for initiative respond more effectively to leaders' behaviors, in that they believe that obstacles will be tackled by top managers in the pursuit of implementation of innovation behavior (Michaelis *et al.*, 2010). On the other hand, job autonomy is expected to reinforce people's innovative behavior given that it revolves around discretion, flexibility and latitude granted by empowering leaders. Empirical evidence has demonstrated that job autonomy mediates the

openness for innovation - innovation performance link (Burcharth *et al.*, 2017). Based on the above, we can predict the following:

Hypothesis 6: There is an indirect, positive link between CEOs' empowering leadership and middle managers' IWB through organizational climate for initiative and job autonomy.

Methods

Procedure

To test the research model of the present investigation, 800 firms located in six major cities in Morocco were approached. The list of these companies was obtained from a governmental source. The selected companies had to have created a brand-new or considerably improved product or production process in the last three years (OECD, 2005). To collect data for the current study, three separate questionnaires were utilized. The first one was destined for CEOs, presidents, or general managers (CEO for short). CEOs provided an assessment of the IWB of their middle managers who are responsible for the production departments. The second questionnaire was designed for the middle managers who provided data about the empowering leadership behavior of their respective CEOs, the job autonomy of their position (mediating variable) as well as their age, education, and company tenure. They were also asked about approximate age, education, and company tenure of their CEO. The last questionnaire gathered data about the second mediating variable (organizational climate for initiative) from four non-managerial employees working in the production division of the same firm.

The purpose of collecting data from three different sources within the same firm was, at least, two-fold: (1) to obtain the right information from the right person: e.g., assessment of middle

manager's innovative work behavior was carried out by the CEO would be more objective and less biased than asking the middle managers themselves; and (2) collecting data using three separate questionnaires allows reducing potential common method bias (Podsakoff et al., 2012).

The survey questions were presented in French. The back-translation approach was utilized (Brislin, 1986) to translate the scales from English to French which is the language of communication generally adopted in the business milieu in Morocco (Benzakour, 2007).

No pilot study was conducted because no new scales were used; the scales used in the study were extensively validated across countries and industries.

Sample

Out of the 800 the firms that accepted to take part in the current research, 444 firms actually participated in the study by having their CEOs, middle managers and employees complete the study questionnaires, which constitutes a response rate of 55.5%. Respondents' firms have an average age of 16.84 years (SD = 8.46). Respondents' firms have an average of 42.4 full time employees. The average age of the CEOs is 50 years (SD = 10.30) and the average tenure in their current position is 12 years (SD = 5.67). In terms of gender, 89.2% of the respondent CEOs are male. As per the education level, 16.4 % of the respondent CEOs have a high school degree or less, 21.6 % a college degree, 29.5% a bachelor's degree, 30% a master's degree, and 2.5% a doctoral degree. Most of the middle managers are male (68.9%). They have an average age of 37.7 years (SD = 6.07) and an average tenure in their present position of 7 years (SD = 3.89). Concerning their education, 4.5% of the respondent middle managers have a high school degree

or less, 14.2 % a college degree, 40.5% a bachelor's degree, 40.5% a master's degree, and 0.2% a doctoral degree.

Measures

Responses to all items of the focal variables were measured with a 5-point scale (1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree).

Empowering leadership. We borrowed the scale created and validated by Ahearne et al. (2005) which is comprised of four dimensions. These dimensions, which include three items each, are enhancing the meaningfulness of work, fostering participation in decision making, expressing confidence in high performance, and providing autonomy from bureaucratic constraints. Sample item is *“My CEO believes in my ability to improve even when I make mistakes”*. This scale was used as a one-dimensional measure in the analyses. In order to obtain a more stable estimation of parameters (Kline, 2015), we proceeded with the theory-based item parceling technique of this measure yielding four parcels corresponding with the four dimensions of the empowering leadership scale.

Climate for initiative. We used the measure that was developed by Frese et al. (1997). Its seven items were slightly reformulated to be used at the organizational level for initiative. A sample item is *“People in our company take initiative immediately - more often than in other companies”*.

Job autonomy. We used the following two-item scale from Piccolo et al. (2010): *“The job gives me a chance to use my personal initiative and judgment in carrying out the work”* and *“The job gives me considerable opportunity for independence and freedom in how I do the work”*.

IWB. It was measured with Scott and Bruce's (1994) scale comprised of six items. A sample item is "My manager of the production department develops adequate plans and schedules for the implementation of new ideas".

Control variables. Variables that have been found to be significantly associated with innovation were controlled for. These are middle managers' and CEOs' age, tenure and education, firm size, and firm age (Stock *et al.*, 2019; Vaccaro *et al.*, 2012). Although industry is a relevant control variable in the innovation literature; nonetheless, it did not significantly correlate with most of the study focal variables.

Data analysis and results

Descriptive analysis

Means, standard deviations, reliabilities and inter-correlations of the model variables are shown in Table 1. Internal consistency reliability coefficients are reported on the diagonal.

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TABLE 1 about here

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Cronbach's alpha for empowering leadership, climate for imitative, and IWB are respectively .780, .898 and .881. These values are higher than the recommended level of .700, which indicates that the reliability level of these scales is acceptable (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). Job autonomy has a Cronbach's alpha of .640 and the Spearman-Brown coefficient is 0.642 which is the most appropriate reliability coefficient for a two-item scale (Eisinga, Grotenhuis, and Pelzer, 2013). These statistics that are under 0.700 threshold are probably due to the fact that the scale is

comprised of two items only; nonetheless, the average inter-item correlation of job autonomy is 0.473, which is indicative of acceptable level of homogeneity (Clark and Watson, 1995). Several scholars support the adequacy of using single items for simple constructs (e.g., Freed, 2013; Grapentine, 2001; Leisen Pollack and Alexandrov, 2013) as they can be used in cases of sufficiently narrow constructs that are unambiguous to the respondents (Freed, 2013), so long as their reliability and validity are not affected (Grapentine, 2001).

The patterns of inter-correlations of the study variables are consistent with the related theoretical insights and research findings. CEOs' empowering leadership is positively linked to middle managers' job autonomy ($r= 0.340$, $p < .01$) and IWB ($r= 0.512$, $p < .01$) as well as climate for initiative ($r= 0.251$, $p < .01$). In addition, middle managers' job autonomy is positively related to their IWB ($r= 0.216$, $p < .01$). Lastly, climate for initiative is positively correlated with middle managers' job autonomy ($r= 0.182$, $p < .01$) and IWB ($r= 0.416$, $p < .01$).

Measurement Model

Loadings of the scales' items were verified. As Table 2 reveals, the values of standardized loadings ranged between 0.559 and 0.919. All the item loadings were statistically significant at the 0.001 level. To assess convergent validity and internal consistency of the research scales, the average variance extracted (AVE) and composite reliability (CR) statistics were computed (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). All the CR values are greater than the AVE values and the latter are higher than 0.5, indicating that the constructs were convergently valid and internally consistent; except for the empowering leadership scale which had a 0.483 AVE value. Nonetheless, given that the hypothesized model is reflective rather than formative, is comprised of low order constructs, and

its CR is above 0.700 (0.787), it still can be considered even with an AVE below 0.500 (Fornell and Lacker, 1981).

The predictive validity of the model is generally acceptable as the percentage of the variance (R-square value) in the mediators that the independent variable (i.e., empowering leadership) explains is 0.342 (job autonomy) and 0.253 (climate for initiative), while the explained variance in the dependent variable (i.e., innovative behavior) is relatively high (0.445).

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TABLE 2 about here

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As recommended by several authors (e.g., Anderson and Gerbing, 1988), the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) technique was used via AMOS 24 to examine the measurement model, the construct validity, and the distinctiveness of the research variables. To do so, chi-square statistics as well as fit indices of comparative fit index (CFI), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), and root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) were computed (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988).

CFA Results in Table 3 show that the 4-factor model has a better fit than the 3-factor, 2-factor, and 1-factor models; the indices are as follows: $\chi^2/df=2.905$; CFI = .941; TLI= .924; and RMSEA= .066. These results also support the distinctiveness of the four variables of the current study for subsequent analyses.

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TABLE 3 about here

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Hypothesis Testing

The study hypotheses were tested using Structural Equation Modelling through AMOS 24 along the Bayesian estimation analysis while controlling for firm age and size (number of employees), middle managers' and CEOs' age, tenure, and education.

Table 4 shows the findings of the direct effects of the structural model. As expected with Hypothesis 1, the CEO's empowering leadership is positively and significantly associated with middle managers' IWB ($\beta = 0.328, p < 0.01; LLCI = 0.238, ULCI = 0.405$). It was also found that CEOs' empowering leadership is positively associated with climate for initiative ($\beta = 0.253, p < 0.01; LLCI = 0.159, ULCI = 0.334$) and job autonomy ($\beta = 0.342, p < 0.01, LLCI = 0.262, ULCI = 0.422$); hence, Hypotheses 2 and 4 were supported. Additionally, the regression coefficient among climate for initiative and middle managers' IWB was 0.290 ($p < .001; LLCI = 0.223, ULCI = 0.355$) and middle managers' job autonomy and their IWB was 0.069 ($p < .05; LLCI = 0.001, ULCI = 0.147$), lending support to Hypotheses 3 and 5.

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TABLE 4 about here

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Hypothesis 6, which posits that there is an indirect, positive link between CEOs' empowering leadership and middle managers' IWB through organizational climate for initiative and job autonomy, was verified using the AMOS 24 bootstrapping technique; the latter is based on the Bayesian estimation approach along the Markov chain Monte Carlo algorithm, that is an estimation of 95% bias-corrected CIs for indirect effects by bootstrapping 22,000 samples.

The hypothesized mediation model fit the data well: $\chi^2/df=1.976$; CFI = 0.993; TLI = 0.956; and RMSEA = .045. Table 5 reveals that the indirect effects of CEOs' empowering leadership towards middle managers' IWB through organizational climate for initiative and middle managers' job autonomy were respectively 0.041 ($p = .032$) and 0.127 ($p = .007$). The total standardized indirect effect of CEOs' empowering leadership onto managers' IWB was also statistically significant (0.167, $p = .009$). The lower boundary of the 95% credible interval for the indirect effect of CEOs' empowering leadership on middle managers' IWB via organizational climate for initiative and middle managers' job autonomy is 0.115 and the corresponding upper boundary value is 0.238.

Therefore, these findings lend support to Hypothesis 6.

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TABLE 5 about here

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Discussion & conclusion

The present study aimed to shed light on the connection between empowering leadership and IWB, while including two mediating variables, namely climate for initiative and job autonomy. Specifically, this study revealed that firms which are led by empowering leaders, that enjoy a climate for initiative and that grant their middle managers (heads of production departments) autonomy in their job, are likely to have their middle managers exhibit IWB.

This study results suggest that empowering leadership is positively associated with IWB. These results corroborate findings that linked empowering leadership to IWB (e.g., Chen *et al.*, 2011) as empowering leaders encourage their subordinates to experiment with innovative ways at work independently from the fear of punishment in case of negative outcomes (Jung *et al.*, 2003).

Further, empowering leaders boost creativity in general (Zhang and Zhou, 2014) as they encourage followers to exhibit pro-active behaviors at work (Martin *et al.*, 2013) due to the trust and confidence they display (Tuckey *et al.*, 2012).

Regarding the positive association between empowering leadership and climate for initiative, empowering leaders permit their firms to provide an initiative-friendly environment to their subordinates. They give followers the freedom to make independent decisions (Forrester, 2000), encourage a strong sense of autonomy among subordinates (Hon and Chan, 2013), and exhort subordinates to act independently, take initiative, and solve problems they encounter at work in a timely manner (Kim and Beehr, 2017). On another note, the findings of the present study are aligned with previous research that has revealed that leaders who emphasize more task performance monitoring than innovation are considered by highly empowered subordinates as controlling and unmotivating, and instigate less IWB (Pieterse *et al.*, 2009).

The findings provide evidence that organizational climate for initiative is positively associated with middle managers' IWB. This is because personal initiative is linked to idea generation (Binnewies *et al.*, 2007) and innovation implementation (Michaelis *et al.*, 2010). In fact, firms that enjoy a strong climate for initiative encourage IWB by granting their members latitude and leeway in the way they accomplish their tasks (Frese *et al.*, 1999). In addition, employees who perceive their companies as having a strong climate for initiative believe that their top managers can remove obstacles during the innovation implementation course (Michaelis *et al.*, 2010).

CEOs' empowering leadership has been found to positively affect middle managers' job autonomy. This conclusion is consistent with extant literature stating that empowering leaders enhance their followers' job autonomy (Arnold *et al.*, 2000; Hon and Chan, 2013; Kim and Beehr, 2017) by, among others, involving them in decision making and removing bureaucratic restrictions

(Ahearne et al., 2005) as well as by urging followers to exhibit pro-active behaviors at work (Hon and Chan, 2013).

The current study shows that middle managers' job autonomy is positively associated with their IWB. This finding is in line with a few studies that confirmed the role of job autonomy in spurring IWB (see Burcharth et al., 2017; De Spiegelaere et al., 2016; Hammond et al., 2011; Slåtten et al., 2011). This association can be explained by the fact that workers tend to be creative when they can choose the way to complete their tasks (Amabile *et al.*, 1996). Further, job autonomy allows people to experiment with new approaches and techniques at work (De Spiegelaere *et al.*, 2016). Lastly, the feeling of autonomy that people sense at work results in a constant motivation to identifying and implementing creative solutions (Deci and Ryan, 1985).

The study demonstrates that climate for initiative and job autonomy mediate the empowering leadership-IWB link. These findings are in line with prior studies stressing the role of organizational leaders' support in positively influencing followers' initiative (Ohly *et al.*, 2006), which, in turn, positively impacts the way followers carry out their jobs (Baer and Frese, 2003). Additionally, job autonomy has also been shown to mediate the relationship between openness for innovation and innovation performance (Burcharth *et al.*, 2017).

An important strength of this study lies in collecting data from different sources. Middle managers provided data about the empowerment leadership behavior of their CEOs (independent variable) and the autonomy in their job (first mediating variable). Assessment of the middle managers' IWB (dependent variable) was conducted by the CEOs. Data about climate for initiative (second mediating variable) were gathered from non-managerial employees working in the production department. This data collection strategy aimed at reducing common method bias (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2012).

Theoretical and practical implications

This study has three main theoretical implications. First, it will add to the leadership literature by examining the relationship between empowering leadership and IWB of middle managers within SMEs in manufacturing industries; it is important to note that the extant literature has mainly focused on other leadership styles (e.g., Choi *et al.*, 2016; Yidong and Xinxin, 2013) and non-managerial employees' IWB with only a few studies that have investigated IWB of managers (Michaelis *et al.*, 2010; Stock *et al.*, 2019). Second, while the extant literature sheds light on the way leadership favors and brings about managers' IWB (Chen *et al.*, 2014), the “when” or under what circumstances IWB takes place (e.g., in a climate for initiative) is still under-researched (Lorinkova *et al.*, 2013). The findings indicate that CEOs' empowering leadership behavior spurs middle managers' IWB when climate for initiative is strong and job autonomy is granted to subordinates within SMEs in manufacturing industries in Morocco. Lastly, as the extant literature has mostly examined the way job-related factors interplay between empowering leadership and IWB (e.g., Gkorezis ,2016; Jada *et al.*, 2019; Slåtten *et al.*, 2011), the current study expands the literature by examining the role of other contextual antecedents of innovation such as climate for initiative and job autonomy. Similarly, this study extends the conceptual boundaries toward an important economic sector, namely manufacturing and expands the geographical area by conducting research in an emerging country in the Middle East and Africa region (i.e., Morocco).

In terms of practical implications, this study has demonstrated that organizational leaders, who urge their middle managers to be innovative in their job, should adopt empowering leadership practices, in light of the case of SMEs in manufacturing industries in Morocco. Designing and providing leadership training programs and activities might assist in developing empowering leaders. Additionally, given the importance of individual innovation, several organizations oblige

their members to perform their duties in a creative manner in order to boost organizational effectiveness (Robinson and Beesley, 2010). To do so, the current study proposes that favorable climate for initiative can be an effective tool to spur organizational members' IWB. In fact, the climate for initiative encourages personal initiative (Baer and Frese, 2003), and directs and supports positive behaviors in developing and implementing new ideas (Binnewies *et al.*, 2007; Frese and Fay, 2001). Therefore, firms that seek to enhance the IWB of their workers ought to bank on the benefits of building a favorable climate for initiative. Lastly, job autonomy has been found to play the role of a mediator in the empowering leadership-IWB link. Thus, organizations should resort to job autonomy as a tool to exhort middle managers to display innovative behavior in their position by granting them independence and discretion in the way they carry out their tasks, particularly that job autonomy is a very influential job characteristic in motivating workers (Morgeson and Humphrey, 2006).

Limitations and future research

This study has three limitations that should be dealt with in future research. As middle managers' IWB was 'subjectively' assessed by their CEOs, future research should use more objective measures to rate IWB. Furthermore, given that we sought to ensure a certain level of homogeneity of the climate of initiative, we included a sample of small and medium businesses; as result, the findings cannot be generalized to larger companies. Hence, future research should tackle the research problem in large firms. Lastly, given that the research design is cross-sectional, cause-effect relationships cannot be inferred. Thus, longitudinal design ought to be used in future research with the aim of assessing causality.

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Table 1. Descriptive statistics and correlations among the study variables

Model Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4
1. Empowering leadership	4.063	.328	(.780)			
2. Climate for initiative	3.242	.826	.251**	(.898)		
3. Job autonomy	3.984	.468	.340**	.182**	(.640)	
4. Innovative work behavior	3.992	.566	.512**	.416**	.216**	(.881)

N = 444. Cronbach α S are reported on the diagonal between brackets. **p < .01.

Table 2. Factor loadings, t-values, AVEs and CRs

Scale	Items/Dimensions	Loading	T-values	AVE	CR
Empowering leadership	Enhancing the meaningfulness of work.	.604**	11.542	0.483	0.787
	Fostering participation in decision making.	.708**	13.333		
	Expressing confidence in high performance.	.670**	12.722		
	Providing autonomy from bureaucratic constraints	.785**	13.333		
Climate for initiative	People in our company actively attack problems.	.782**	13.504	0.576	0.889
	Whenever something goes wrong, people in our company search for a solution immediately.	.851**	14.300		
	Whenever there is a chance to get actively involved, people in our company take it.	.773**	13.400		
	People in our company take initiative immediately - more often than in other companies.	.784**	16.293		
	People in our company use opportunities quickly in order to attain goals.	.759**	14.034		
	People in our company usually do more than they are asked to do.	.574**	10.981		
	People in our company are particularly good at realizing ideas.	.650**	10.981		
Job autonomy	The job gives me a chance to use my personal initiative and judgment in carrying out the work	.848**	6.056	0.516	0.672
	The job gives me considerable opportunity for independence and freedom in how I do the work'	.559**	6.056		
Innovative behavior	Searches out new technologies, processes, techniques and/or product ideas	.778**	9.921	0.596	0.897
	Generates creative ideas	.833**	10.284		
	Promotes and champions ideas to others	.714**	10.697		
	Investigates and secures funds needed to implement new ideas	.919**	12.917		
	Develops adequate plans and schedules for the implementation of new ideas	.730**	16.479		
	Is innovative.	.623**	9.921		

**p < .01.

Table 3 Test results of alternative models

Model	χ^2	Df	χ^2/df	$\Delta\chi^2$	CFI	TLI	RMSEA
4-Factor model ^a	383.457	132	2.905	-	0.941	0.924	0.066
3-Factor model ^b	443.826	131	3.388	60.369**	0.927	0.904	0.073
2-Factor model ^c	468.062	130	3.600	24.236**	0.921	0.896	0.076
1-Factor model ^d	618.232	128	4.830	150.17**	0.885	0.846	0.093

^a Hypothesized model; ^b Empowering Leadership and Climate for Initiative merged; ^c Empowering Leadership, Climate for Initiative and Job Autonomy merged; ^d All items load on one single factor. ** $p < .01$ (two tailed tests).

Table 4 Results of direct effects

Regression paths	Hypothesis	Estimate	Remarks
EL → IWB	H 1	0.328***	Supported
EL → CI	H 2	0.253***	Supported
CI → IWB	H 3	0.290***	Supported
EL → JA	H 4	0.342***	Supported
JA → IWB	H 5	0.069*	Supported

EL: empowering leadership; IWB: innovative work behavior; CI: climate for initiative; JA: job autonomy.
Significance: *** $p < .001$, * $p < .05$.

Table 5 Results of indirect effects

Regression paths (Hypothesis 6)	Estimated indirect effect	Bootstrap 95% CI		<i>p</i> value
		Lower	Upper	
EL → CI → IWB	0.041*	0.006	0.073	.032
EL → JA → IWB	0.127**	0.087	0.182	.007
Sum	0.167**	0.115	0.238	.009

EL: empowering leadership; IWB: innovative work behavior; CI: climate for initiative; JA: job autonomy.
Significance: ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$